

FROM REJECTION TO REDIRECTION: UNDERSTANDING THE PATHS OF NON-ACCEPTED BSED SOCIAL STUDIES APPLICANTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the socio-demographic and academic profiles of applicants who were not accepted into the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Social Studies program at Negros Oriental State University–Guihulngan Campus for Academic Year 2024–2025. Specifically, it sought to identify the reasons for their non-acceptance, determine the academic or career pathways they pursued afterward, and examine the relationship between their profiles and the factors leading to rejection. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from rejected applicants and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, and the chi-square test of independence. Results revealed that the majority of rejected applicants were female (84%), aged 17–19 years (84%), and graduates of public high schools (90%). Although most respondents demonstrated strong academic performance, with 71% obtaining general point averages (GPAs) ranging from 90–100%, a substantial proportion (68%) reported reviewing for less than one week prior to the entrance examination. Failure in the entrance examination emerged as the primary reason for non-acceptance (84%), followed by failure in the screening process (13%). Following rejection, most respondents enrolled in private higher education institutions (77%), while others pursued employment, took a gap year, or explored alternative educational pathways. Chi-square analysis revealed no significant relationship between applicants' socio-demographic or academic profiles and the reasons for rejection. These findings suggest that performance in the entrance examination and screening process plays a more decisive role in admission outcomes than applicants' background characteristics.

Keywords: *Academic profiling, Admission screening process, Entrance examination performance, Higher education admissions, Rejected applicants, Socio-demographic profile, State university admissions, Teacher education program (BSED), State university admissions*

INTRODUCTION

Access to higher education is universally recognized as a fundamental driver of socio-economic development and individual empowerment. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education emphasizes the importance of ensuring inclusive and equitable education while promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. However, despite efforts to expand access, various barriers continue to prevent students, particularly those from marginalized and economically disadvantaged backgrounds, from successfully enrolling in higher education institutions.

Human Capital Theory suggests that investments in education enhance an individual's productivity and economic potential. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) highlights the transformative role of education in fostering economic growth, reducing inequality, and strengthening social cohesion (UNESCO, 2022). State universities, including Negros Oriental State University (NORSU), play a crucial role in making higher education more accessible by providing affordable opportunities for students from low-income backgrounds. However, limited capacity and competitive admissions often result in many applicants being denied entry.

In the Philippines, policies such as the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act of 2017 (Republic Act No. 10931) aim to remove financial barriers to higher education through tuition subsidies and financial aid. While these efforts improve affordability, access remains a challenge, particularly for high-demand programs with stringent admission criteria. At NORSU-Guihulngan, the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Social Studies is one such program where competitive requirements lead to the rejection of numerous applicants each year. While much attention is given to successful enrollees, little is known about the experiences of those who fail to gain admission.

Existing studies, such as Shamsaldeen et al. (2024), have examined broad issues related to higher education access, including entrance exam limitations, socio-economic disparities, and systemic barriers. However, these studies do not specifically address the experiences of rejected applicants in regional state universities or examine the academic and socio-demographic factors that influence non-acceptance. Furthermore, there is limited research on the educational and career pathways pursued by students after rejection, leaving a gap in understanding how access to higher education shapes life trajectories.

This study seeks to address this gap by focusing on unsuccessful applicants to the BSED-Social Studies program at NORSU-Guihulngan. It will examine their socio-demographic and academic profiles, identify the specific reasons for their non-

acceptance, and explore their subsequent educational or employment decisions. The study will not be limited to students from specific high schools but will include applicants from various schools across different backgrounds. By analyzing these challenges, the research aims to contribute to policies and interventions that enhance access to higher education and support students in overcoming barriers to university admission.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the reasons for non-acceptance into state universities, specifically at NORSU Guihulngan – BSED Social Studies program, and the subsequent educational or employment paths taken by applicants. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic and academic profile of applicants who were not accepted into NORSU Guihulngan – BSED Social Studies program in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Academic performance (SHS GPA)
 - 1.4. Type of high school attended
 - 1.5. Time spent reviewing for the entrance exam?
2. What are the specific reasons for non-acceptance into NORSU Guihulngan – BSED Social Studies program?
3. What educational or employment paths do non-accepted applicants pursue following their non-acceptance, in terms of:
 - 3.1. Enrolling in other program
 - 3.2. Enrolling in private institutions
 - 3.3. Taking vocational training
 - 3.4. Entering the workforce
 - 3.5. Took a year gap (did not enroll or work)?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic and academic profile of applicants, and the specific reasons for their non – acceptance to NORSU Guihulngan – BSED Social Studies program?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic profile of applicants, and the specific reasons for their non – acceptance to NORSU Guihulngan – BSED Social Studies program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the challenges encountered by applicants who were not accepted into the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies (BSED – Social Studies) program at Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) Guihulngan. The study focuses on quantitative data collected through structured survey questionnaires. The descriptive aspect of the

research aims to present a comprehensive profile of the non-accepted applicants in terms of their age, sex, senior high school GPA, type of high school attended, and the amount of time they spent reviewing for the entrance exam. It also seeks to identify the specific reasons for their non-acceptance into the program and the various educational or employment paths they pursued afterward, such as enrolling in private institutions, taking vocational training, entering the workforce, or taking a year gap. Meanwhile, the correlational aspect of the study examines whether there is a significant relationship between the applicants' socio-demographic and academic profiles and the specific reasons for their rejection. This design is suitable for the study as it allows for a systematic and focused analysis of admission outcomes, helping to identify patterns and factors that may influence access to higher education, particularly for those who made Social Studies their first-choice program but were not admitted.

Environment

This study was conducted in Guihulngan City, located in Negros Oriental, Philippines. Guihulngan City has limited higher education options, with Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) Guihulngan being the primary state-funded institution offering affordable tertiary education to local students. The city is predominantly rural, with most residents relying on agriculture and small-scale businesses, making access to higher education a significant socio-economic challenge. Conducting the study in Guihulngan City provided a focused view of the educational barriers faced by students in economically disadvantaged regions, where limited resources and opportunities often restrict access to higher education.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were applicants to Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) Guihulngan who were not accepted into the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies (BSED – Social Studies) program for the academic year 2024–2025, despite choosing it as their first priority. The list of first-priority applicants was obtained from the NORSU CARE Center. From this list, those who were included in the final list of qualified or enrolled students were excluded.

To ensure that only directly rejected applicants were included, each individual on the list was contacted personally and informed about the nature of the study. They were instructed to respond to the survey only if they had undergone the screening process for the BSED – Social Studies program and were formally not accepted. Those who voluntarily shifted to another course or did not complete the screening process were advised not to participate. Applicants who could not be reached through any means were excluded from the study. This approach allowed the researchers to eliminate individuals who were not officially rejected from the program. The results were presented in tables and interpreted accordingly.

The study employed a purposive sampling technique, focusing on applicants who genuinely intended to enter the Social Studies program but were unable to do so due to

non-acceptance. This ensured that the data gathered was specific to the barriers experienced by this group.

Table 1. Total Number of Respondents

Total no. of applicants	Total number of unaccepted applicants				Total no. of respondents (directly rejected only)
	Directly rejected	Indirectly rejected	Did not reach	Total	
72	31	10	6	47	31

Instrument

This study utilized a self-made structured survey questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire is designed to gather quantitative data from respondents and is composed of closed-ended questions to ensure consistency and ease of analysis. It consists of four sections: (1) Socio-Demographic and Academic Profile, (2) Reasons for Non-Acceptance, (3) Educational and Employment Path After Non-Acceptance, and (4) Additional Insights.

The first section collects background Information, age, sex, senior high school GPA, type of high school attended, and time spent reviewing for the entrance exam. The second section identifies the reasons for non-acceptance into the Bachelor of Secondary Education Social Studies program at NORSU Guihulngan, with predefined options such as failing the entrance exam, not meeting grade requirements, failing the screening process. The third section examines respondents' choices after rejection, whether they pursued further education in another institution, enrolled in vocational training, entered the workforce, or took a gap year. The final section gathers insights for the preparation to the university's admission process.

During the questionnaire validation process, researchers utilized a validation tool with a rating scale ranging from 1 to 5: 5 – very much valid, 4 – very valid, 3 – moderately valid, 2 – not so valid, and 1 – not valid. The questionnaires underwent expert validation by Eden Grace Tabanao, Ph.D. , Von Bruun M. Pelletero, Ph.D and Adven Sheila T. Antiquando, Ph.D. The validity result yielded a score of 4.67, indicating that the questionnaire is highly valid and meets the criteria for reliability assessment.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection for this study was conducted during the academic year 2024–2025 and focused on individuals who applied to Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) Guihulngan for the Bachelor of Secondary Education – Social Studies program but were not accepted. The full list of first-priority applicants was obtained from the NORSU CARE Center, and those who were accepted or enrolled in the program were removed from the list. Only those who were directly rejected were invited to participate.

To ensure that only qualified respondents answered the survey, each applicant was personally messaged and informed that only those who had been formally rejected from the Social Studies program should participate. Those who shifted to another course or did not complete the screening process were asked not to respond. The survey was distributed exclusively through Google Forms for ease of access and convenience. Before accessing the questionnaire, participants were asked to read and agree to an informed consent form, which explained the study's purpose, voluntary nature, and confidentiality measures. The structured questionnaire contained closed-ended questions, categorized into sections on socio-demographic background, academic profile, reasons for non-acceptance, and post-rejection educational or employment paths. Data collection spanned approximately one month, with reminders sent to improve response rates.

All responses were reviewed for completeness. Incomplete or unclear entries were excluded from the analysis to maintain validity. The data was stored securely, with digital responses kept in a password-protected file. No personally identifiable information was included in the analysis; only aggregated data were used in the final presentation of results.

Treatment of Data

For this study, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, ranking were used to summarize the respondents' socio-demographic profiles, reasons for non-acceptance, and their paths after rejection. Cross-tabulation analysis was applied to examine relationships between categorical variables, such as the connection between socio-demographic and academic, performance and reasons for non-acceptance. To determine whether these relationships were statistically significant, the Chi-square test was utilized. Microsoft Excel was also used, particularly in calculating Chi-square values and critical values. This analytical approach allowed the study to identify patterns and insights regarding the challenges faced by unsuccessful applicants of NORSU Guihulngan Campus' Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies program. The results were presented in tables and interpreted accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile

Table 1.1 Descriptive statistics of the demographic profile of the respondents (n= 31)

Variable	Description	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Age Group	17-19 years old	26	84	1
	20-22 years old	5	16	2
	23-25 years old	0	0	-
	26 years old and above	0	0	-

Sex	Male	5	16	2
	Female	26	84	1
Total		31	100	

Table 1.1 shows that most respondents (84%) are aged 17–19, with the remainder (16%) aged 20–22, and none older than 22. This concentration of younger applicants suggests that the study primarily reflects the experiences of fresh senior high graduates. From an Equity Theory perspective, age itself is less a barrier than the support systems available to these youth, such as family encouragement and access to preparatory resources. The Republic Act No. 10931 (Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act) emphasizes equitable access for all qualified youth, regardless of background, aiming to reduce socio-economic disparities that can affect educational opportunities. However, age-related factors, such as maturity and readiness, may intersect with social and economic support, impacting access.

According to Goodman, Gregg, and Washbrook (2011) found that children’s educational attainment is more closely influenced by aspirations, attitudes, and family support rather than age alone. Similarly, this aligns with Falcon (2015) who found that age is not a primary determinant of college success, suggesting that the youth of respondents does not necessarily disadvantage them in accessing higher education, unless compounded by other factors.

The second row presents the sex distribution of respondents, revealing that 84% (26) were female and only 16% (5) were male. This notable disparity suggests that female applicants were more prominently represented among those not accepted into the BSED Social Studies program at NORSU-Guihulngan. Based on Equity Theory, this raises concerns about whether both sexes had equal access to preparatory resources or faced different expectations during the application process. While the data does not indicate bias in the admissions process itself, it highlights the importance of addressing gender-based support mechanisms. In line with Magna Carta of Women (RA 9710), which mandates equal opportunities for women in education, this distribution may also reflect higher educational aspirations among females or a greater willingness to engage in research. Ensuring gender equity means assessing not only who applies and gets accepted but also the systemic factors that influence outcomes across sexes.

A 2015 analysis by Money magazine highlighted that certain U.S. colleges admitted women at significantly higher rates than men (Glamour, 2015). For instance, Harvey Mudd College had an acceptance rate for women 2.5 times higher than for men. Similar trends were observed at institutions like MIT and Caltech.

Table 1.2. Descriptive Statistics of the Academic Profile of the Respondents (n=31)

Variables	Description	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
	(80-84%)	0	0	-
	(85-89%)	9	29	2

Academic Performance (SHS GPA)	(90-100%)	22	71	1
Type of High School Last Attended	Public	28	90	1
	Private	3	10	2
	Alternative Learning System (ALS)	0	0	-
Time Spent Reviewing	Less than 1 week	21	68	1
	1-2 weeks	10	32	2
	3-4 weeks	0	0	-
	More than 1 month	0	0	-
	Total	31	100	

This section examines the academic profile of non-accepted Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Social Studies applicants at NORSU-Guihulngan. It focuses on three key variables SHS academic performance, type of high school attended, and entrance exam preparation time to assess both cognitive readiness and educational equity. Guided by Equity Theory, this analysis explores whether high-performing yet rejected applicants were given fair opportunities to succeed. Patterns in the data will be critically interpreted, with insights informing practice, policy, and theory. Relevant literature provides context within broader discussions on fairness and educational access.

The first row presents the academic performance (SHS GPA) reveals that most respondents (71%) had a Senior High School GPA between 90–100%, while the remaining 29% scored between 85–89%. No respondents had GPAs below 85%, indicating that all participants showed strong academic performance. Despite these high grades, they were still not accepted into the BSED–Social Studies program. This reflects a core concern of Equity Theory that effort (in this case, strong academic performance) does not always lead to fair outcomes. When academically qualified students are rejected, it may create a perception of inequity in the admission process. This suggests a need to re-evaluate admission policies to ensure that high-performing students are given equitable consideration, possibly by incorporating GPA as a stronger factor alongside entrance exams.

A study conducted by the National Association for College Admission Counseling (NACAC) revealed that college acceptance rates are positively influenced by higher GPAs. Students with high GPAs have a greater likelihood of being accepted into their preferred colleges and universities.

The second row explores the educational background of the non-accepted BSED Social Studies applicants at NORSU-Guihulngan, with particular attention to the type of high school last attended. This variable offers insight into the foundational learning environments of applicants and the possible disparities in access to college preparatory resources that influence their admission outcomes. As shown in the table, a significant majority of the applicants (90%) graduated from public high schools, while a smaller

percentage (10%) came from private institutions. Notably, none of the respondents had a background in technical-vocational institutions such as TESDA-accredited schools.

This suggests that most of the applicants who failed to gain admission were products of the public school system. While public schools provide broader access to secondary education, especially for economically disadvantaged students, they often face resource limitations that can affect students' preparedness for competitive college entrance exams. According to Equity Theory (Adams, 1963), this distribution raises questions about fairness in the selection process. Equity Theory posits that individuals assess fairness based on the ratio of inputs (such as effort, resources, and preparation) to outcomes (like admission or rejection). Public school graduates may be exerting comparable effort but lack access to preparatory advantages such as review centers, testing simulations, or personalized academic guidance commonly available in private schools.

This implies a systemic imbalance that state universities must address not through equal treatment but through equitable support systems. Policies like free pre-entrance review programs, targeted outreach to public schools, or the inclusion of contextualized admissions criteria that consider school background could help level the playing field. These strategies are consistent with the intent of Republic Act No. 10931, which guarantees access to quality tertiary education, particularly for students from underserved sectors.

International evidence supports the idea that students from public schools are not inherently less capable. For instance, Solomon Admissions Consulting (2019) reported that in Fall 2019, public school students applying to top universities in the U.S. had a 72.5% acceptance rate, which was higher than the 62.5% rate for private school applicants. This suggests that when given equitable opportunities and support, public school students can perform just as well or even better than their private school counterparts. In the context of NORSU-Guihulngan, this finding underscores the need to recognize and address educational background disparities, not merely in terms of institutional prestige, but in the availability of support mechanisms that directly affect entrance exam readiness and overall college access. Equity, therefore, must not be limited to offering the same admissions exam to everyone, but should include proactive interventions that empower public school graduates to compete fairly.

This last row presents the academic preparation of the non-accepted BSED Social Studies applicants at NORSU-Guihulngan, specifically focusing on the amount of time spent reviewing for the entrance examination. Review time is a key variable in understanding the extent of effort and access to preparatory resources among applicants. As shown in the data, a majority of respondents (68%) reported reviewing for less than one week before the entrance exam, while 32% reviewed for one to two weeks. Notably, none of the applicants studied for more than two weeks. This trend suggests that most applicants had a relatively short preparation period, which may reflect limited access to review materials, structured guidance, or even sufficient time to study due to competing responsibilities or resource constraints.

According to Equity Theory, which emphasizes the balance between inputs (efforts) and outcomes (rewards or opportunities), the findings imply a misalignment. Although the applicants exerted some level of effort, the limited time spent on review may not reflect a lack of motivation but rather unequal conditions such as the absence of tutoring support, inadequate study environments, or lack of access to quality preparatory materials. These disadvantages may undermine the fairness of the admissions process, especially when compared to applicants who may have had the privilege of longer and more structured preparation.

The implications of these findings suggest that institutions like NORSU could explore implementing pre-admission interventions, such as review classes, peer mentoring, or online preparatory sessions targeted at students from under-resourced communities. These strategies could help level the playing field and ensure that all applicants regardless of background are equally prepared to take high-stakes entrance examinations.

Scholarly literature supports the link between review time and academic performance. Pathak (2020) implies that poor or rushed study habits are often linked to academic stress and subpar outcomes in entrance exams. Furthermore, students with less time to prepare may experience heightened anxiety, further reducing their chances of success. In this light, equitable educational access is not only a matter of policy but also of ensuring fair processes and support structures that address the diverse realities of student applicants.

2. Reasons for Non-Acceptance

Table 2.1. Descriptive statistics of the Reasons for Non-Acceptance (n=31)

Reasons for non-acceptance	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Failed entrance exam	26	84	1
Did not pass the screening process	4	13	2
Others	1	3	3
Total	31	100	

This section explores the key reasons for the non-acceptance of applicants into the BSED – Social Studies program at NORSU–Guihulngan. Understanding these reasons is crucial to identifying structural barriers and designing more equitable admission systems. As presented in the data, the overwhelming majority of respondents (84%) cited failure to pass the entrance exam as the reason for their rejection. A smaller portion (13%) failed to pass the screening or interview stage, while only 3% categorized

under “Others,” which referred to a case of failing to meet the time limit for taking the entrance exam, and was consequently marked as not having passed. Significantly, none of the respondents were rejected due to low academic grades, which suggests that most applicants met the minimum GPA requirements but were unable to progress beyond the standardized entry procedures.

According to Equity Theory, this outcome indicates a perceived mismatch between applicants' inputs such as their sustained academic effort during high school and the institutional outcomes they received. When students who have performed well academically are still denied admission due to a single exam result, it raises questions about fairness and access. Particularly for students from public high schools or under-resourced communities, the inability to afford or access review materials or structured preparation may disadvantage them in the competitive admissions process. The high percentage (84%) filtered out by the entrance exam emphasizes the need for institutions to re-evaluate whether this tool alone can fairly assess a student’s potential to succeed in the program.

To further address this, NORSU and similar state universities could consider adopting more inclusive admission strategies. These may include offering free or subsidized review sessions, providing diagnostic exams with feedback before the formal test, or integrating holistic admissions criteria that take into account both academic records and socioeconomic context. Such measures would help mitigate systemic inequities and allow qualified but disadvantaged students to compete more fairly.

3. Path After Non-Acceptance

Table 3.1. Descriptive Statistics of the Path After Non-Acceptance (n=31)

Educational And Employment Path After Non-Acceptance	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Enrolled In a Private University	24	77	1
Entered the Workforce	2	7	3
Took a gap year (did not enroll or work)	1	3	4
Others	4	13	2
Total	31	100	

Table 3.1. above shows that 77% of non-accepted applicants pursued enrollment in private universities, indicating a strong commitment to continuing their education despite rejection from NORSU. A smaller percentage (12.8%) fall into “others” with specific reasons; enroll in other university, enrolled in a public university in Cebu City, enrolled in another program and enroll in public university. 6.5% entered the workforce, and 3.2% took a gap year without engaging in work or studies. No respondents opted for vocational or technical training. According to Equity Theory, this outcome reflects students' efforts to restore perceived balance after experiencing rejection, by seeking

alternative opportunities despite possible financial or institutional barriers. However, access to private education often requires greater economic input, potentially reinforcing systemic inequities. This suggests a need for inclusive policies, such as expanded access to government scholarships, referral systems for vocational institutions, or reapplication support programs for state universities. These policies would promote fairness in educational outcomes and ensure that rejection does not disproportionately burden those from less advantaged backgrounds.

According to Wang and Tengyao (2023), many students who are not accepted into public universities, enrolling in private higher education institutions becomes the most accessible alternative. It is stated that students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds in the Philippines and other developing countries often pursue private university education after facing barriers in public admissions, despite the higher financial burden.

4. Summary of Correlation Between Academic Profile and Reason for Non-Acceptance

Table 4.1. Summary of Correlation Between Academic Profile and Reason for Non Acceptance

Variable	Chi-square Value (χ^2)	Critical Value	Decision for Ho	Remark
Age	0.43	5.991	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Sex	1.14	5.991	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
SHS GPA	3.74	5.991	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Type of High School Last Attended	1.29	5.991	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Time Spent Reviewing	0.63	5.991	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

The results of the Chi-square tests revealed that there is no statistically significant relationship between the applicants' sociodemographic and academic profiles and the specific reasons for their non-acceptance into the BSED Social Studies program at NORSU Guihulngan. Using a significance level of 0.05 and a critical value of 5.991 (df = 2), all computed Chi-square values for the tested variables were lower than the critical value. Specifically, age ($\chi^2 = 0.43$), sex ($\chi^2 = 1.14$), SHS GPA ($\chi^2 = 3.74$), type of high school last attended ($\chi^2 = 1.29$), and time spent reviewing for the entrance exam ($\chi^2 = 0.63$) all fell below the threshold. These findings indicate that none of these variables had a meaningful or significant association with the reasons for rejection, such as failing the exam, not passing the screening process, or other causes. Therefore, the null hypothesis

was not rejected for all variables, suggesting that the reasons for non-acceptance are not dependent on the sociodemographic or academic characteristics measured in this study.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study revealed that the majority of applicants who were not accepted into the NORSU Guihulngan BSED–Social Studies program were young females aged 17–19, with strong academic records from public high schools. Despite their commendable GPAs, most were unable to pass the entrance exam, which emerged as the primary barrier to admission. Limited preparation time for the exam was also a notable trend, suggesting a gap in readiness or access to review resources. Following their rejection, most respondents remained academically persistent by enrolling in private universities, while only a few pursued employment or took a gap year. These findings emphasize the need for enhanced support mechanisms, such as structured review sessions and better exam preparation strategies, to improve access and success rates in state university admissions.

Recommendations

The last part of the survey included a list of suggested interventions, and respondents were asked to select which ones they believed were most needed; their responses were then analyzed to guide the formulation of recommendations. Based on the results of the study, it is recommended that NORSU Guihulngan develop institutional measures to support applicants in preparing for the entrance exam, which was identified as the primary barrier to admission. In response to the respondents' suggestions, the university could establish formal pre-admission review programs or partner with senior high schools to conduct orientation sessions on entrance exam coverage and strategies. Policy-wise, NORSU may consider implementing a standardized pre-entry review assistance policy that includes distribution of study guides, access to mock exams, and provision of consultation sessions through the guidance office. Additionally, incorporating advisory services that help applicants understand what to expect before and during the screening process may bridge the information gap. While only a few respondents suggested digital literacy training, this can still be offered optionally, especially for applicants from public schools who may have limited digital exposure. These actions aim not to compromise admission standards but to ensure that all applicants, especially those from under-resourced backgrounds, are better equipped to meet them.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research standards to safeguard participants' rights and uphold the integrity of the data-gathering process. Before answering the survey, participants were presented with an informed consent section at the beginning of the Google Form, which clearly explained the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Only those who agreed to the terms of the consent were allowed to proceed with the survey.

To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, the questionnaire did not collect any personally identifiable information. All responses were kept strictly anonymous and stored in a password-protected digital file, accessible only to the researchers. No physical documents were involved. The data were reported only in summarized form, ensuring that individual participants could not be identified in any part of the results. Participants had the option to skip any question they found sensitive, and no form of coercion was used. Instructions were clearly provided to ensure that all participants understood the survey items. By following these ethical protocols, the researchers ensured that the study respected participants' autonomy, privacy, and well-being, while also protecting the credibility and reliability of the research process.

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